

ARISTOTELES

OUR THIRD
NEWSLETTER IS OUT!

ARISTOTELES 3rd Newsletter!

Dear reader,

Welcome to the latest edition of the **ARISTOTELES Newsletter**, your biannual source for insights, updates, and highlights from our pioneering project at the intersection of artificial intelligence and personalised medicine.

ARISTOTELES is a groundbreaking project focused on developing **novel artificial intelligence (AI) approaches for personalised medicine**. We're working to create a multinational harmonised data platform that will enable us to better manage complex diseases with multiple interacting pathways. Our goal is to develop personalised AI approaches capable of predicting the risks of comorbidities to shape the future of personalised medicine.

In this issue, we share insights from our recent consortium meeting, updates on clustering activities and collaborations with other EU-funded projects. You'll also meet some of the brilliant minds behind ARISTOTELES through interviews with our researchers, and get the latest on our ongoing activities and deliverables.

Enjoy the read!

The ARISTOTELES Team

Our Coordinator and Principal Investigators

The ARISTOTELES project represents a unique opportunity to explore the real-world impact of AI in managing atrial fibrillation — a complex and increasingly common condition. Our goal is to translate data and evidence from large trials into informed, individualized clinical decisions, always preserving the physician's central role. This project not only fosters innovation in care but also offers a vital learning platform for the next generation of clinicians and researchers across Europe.

Prof. Giuseppe Boriani
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia

Prof. Gregory Lip
University of Liverpool

The ARISTOTELES project is a novel and innovative initiative harnessing the power of AI to transform the management of atrial fibrillation — the most common cardiac rhythm disorder and a growing public health challenge. Our unique multidisciplinary collaboration brings together data scientists and clinicians, enabling the translation of cutting-edge AI into real-world clinical practice. We're excited by the opportunities this project presents, not only for AF care, but for broader applications across other long-term chronic conditions.

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WP3: SURVEY, DISCUSSION GROUPS AND CO-PRODUCTION

Work Package 3 welcomed a new member to the team in April 2025, Dr Anthony Crozier. We have been working towards obtaining stakeholder views on their understanding of, acceptability, and engagement with AI for use in healthcare to inform the co-creation of the AI tool interfaces (Figure 1). The University of Liverpool, together with our partners, Universities of Crete, Modena, Murcia and 'Carol Davila' Bucharest, developed two separate surveys, one for patients and members of the public, and one for healthcare professionals (HCPs). In addition, to finding out more about people's knowledge of AI and their perceptions about its' use for healthcare, we are also gathering information on potential barriers and facilitators of implementation of trustworthy AI-based healthcare.

Figure 1: Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 for WP2- Investigation of AI acceptability and AI tool interface design

The survey development was completed in June 2024 following consortium and patient/public involvement group feedback. Ethical and regulatory approvals were obtained in Greece, Italy, Romania, Spain and the UK over a 7-month period and the surveys were translated, to enable their distribution. Recruitment for the survey commenced in March 2025. To date, 667 patients and members of the public, and 244 HCPs have been recruited.

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WP3 has also created the focus group topic guides for implementation within the discussion groups and co-production workshops (Figure 2), which is the next stage of the work package. We are currently recruiting participants for these workshops, ranging from patients and members of the public to healthcare professionals who manage patients with atrial fibrillation, to software engineers, data scientists and experts in AI technology.

Figure 2: WP3 will follow a collaborative co-design pathway to co-produce the AI tool interfaces

UoL has met with our partners, AI Talentum and LJMU (WP5), to discuss the development of the AI tools (Figure 2). AI Talentum have drafted some mock-ups of the type of AI interfaces we are aiming to co-produce to provide the stakeholders with a better understanding of goals of the project for the co-production workshops, which will involve about 50 people. We are really looking forward to hearing patient and other stakeholder views, understanding, acceptability and engagement with AI for healthcare in the discussion groups which are starting soon.

LAUNCH OF THE ARISTOTELES DATA SCIENCE PLATFORM

We are excited to announce the recent launch of the **ARISTOTELES Data Science Platform**, a robust and scalable infrastructure designed to enable standardized analyses and model development based on real-world health data.

The platform integrates data from individuals diagnosed with atrial fibrillation, drawing from both **Cegedim Health Data's THIN database** and **Danish population-based registries**. The resulting dataset comprises information from 680,341 individuals and includes 281,670,079 clinical measurements, all harmonized using the **OMOP Common Data Model (CDM)**. This represents a significant advancement in supporting scalable, reproducible research across international healthcare data sources.

The ARISTOTELES Platform is hosted within a secure, high-performance computing environment at the **Danish National Genome Centre (DNGC)**, under the governance of the Danish Ministry of Health. This environment is purpose-built for the secure handling and processing of sensitive health data, supporting national efforts in personalized medicine.

In addition to the data infrastructure, we have developed a **robustness suite** to assess the reliability of models applied to OMOP CDM-formatted data. This suite enables automated and systematic evaluation of model performance by identifying and quantifying error patterns that may affect results. It is grounded in the Kahn et al. [1] framework, adopted by the OHDSI community, which evaluates electronic health record (EHR) data quality across three dimensions:

- **Conformance** (adherence to data standards),
- **Completeness** (presence of missing values), and
- **Plausibility** (believability of data values).

The robustness suite applies OHDSI's established data quality checks, focusing on variables relevant to our models, and generates a comprehensive list of quantified error patterns to support reliable model assessment.

For further information about the ARISTOTELES Data Science Platform, including details on ETL processes, data quality assessment, and data access, please contact us directly.

[1] Kahn MG et al., A Harmonized Data Quality Assessment Terminology and Framework for the Secondary Use of Electronic Health Record Data. EGEMS (Wash DC). 2016 Sep 11;4(1):1244. doi: 10.13063/2327-9214.1244.

WP6 CLINICAL TRIAL SIMULATIONS

In silico clinical trials (ISCTs) are clinical trials performed entirely on a computer with virtual patients (VPs) and algorithms assigning treatments and evaluating outcomes. For the ARISTOTELES project, we will develop an ISCT to **compare the management of AF patients with the support of an AI-risk tool versus the usual-care** (Figure 1). The AI-risk tool, from WP5, will provide clinicians with prognostic information regarding a patient's risk of developing specific comorbidities in the future.

The first step in constructing the ISCT is to generate a virtual population representative of AF patients. We utilise **longitudinal health records curated by WP4**, extract relevant patient characteristics, and build machine learning models to generate VPs that are statistically indistinguishable from the real patients. Being computational simulations, each VP can serve as their own control, thus allowing different stratification methods to be compared within an individual. Therefore, each VP is assigned a risk score by the AI-risk tool while simultaneously receiving the standard-of-care.

To enable automated treatment assignment in the ISCT, real patient data—with and without risk scores—are first subjected to a standardised clinical assessment to determine appropriate treatment pathways. These results are then used to train an algorithm capable of automatically assigning treatments to VPs. Finally, to evaluate treatment outcomes, real patients with known outcomes are sorted into the predefined treatment pathways. This information is then used to develop a statistical model for each treatment arm, enabling the prediction of outcomes for VPs.

Once all elements of the ISCT are in place, we can evaluate the efficacy of the AI-risk tool by **comparing treatment outcomes between AI-risk tool-supported care and usual-care**. To validate the ISCT model, we will use patient data from the **randomised controlled trial (RCT)** conducted by WP7 and compare the ISCT-predicted outcomes with the observed RCT outcomes at 1-year follow-up. We will then extend the ISCT to 5 years to assess the impact of the AI-risk tool over a longer period of time.

Publication alert

A EUROPEAN-MULTICENTER NETWORK FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO MANAGE COMPLEXITY AND COMORBIDITIES OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION PATIENTS

The ARISTOTELES Consortium has recently published an article titled "**A European-Multicenter Network for the Implementation of Artificial Intelligence to Manage Complexity and Comorbidities of Atrial Fibrillation Patients**" in TH Open . Authored by Giuseppe Boriani, Davide Antonio Mei, Gregory Y.H. Lip on behalf of the ARISTOTELES partners, this publication outlines the consortium's vision for integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into the clinical management of atrial fibrillation (AF), particularly in patients with complex comorbidities.

The article emphasizes the establishment of a European multicentre network aimed at developing and implementing **AI-driven tools to enhance patient care**. By leveraging machine learning and predictive analytics, the consortium seeks to improve risk stratification, personalize treatment pathways, and optimize outcomes for AF patients. The approach aligns with the **ABC** (Avoid stroke, Better symptom management, Cardiovascular risk and comorbidity optimization) pathway, promoting a holistic, patient-centered strategy.

This publication represents one of the consortium's early contributions to the scientific community, highlighting the collaborative efforts across multiple European institutions to address the challenges of AF management through technological innovation.

Authors: Giuseppe Boriani, Davide Antonio Mei, Gregory Y H Lip, on behalf of the ARISTOTELES Consortium

[READ THE FULL PAPER HERE!](#)

CLUSTERING ACTIVITY

On April 9th, 2025, Aalborg University hosted a hybrid webinar titled Digital Health and AI Technology, marking an important collaboration among the ARISTOTELES, AFFIRMO, and TARGET projects. This event, which was part of a cluster of EU-funded initiatives, brought together medical students, researchers, and healthcare professionals to explore the evolving role of artificial intelligence (AI) in clinical decision-making.

The webinar, centered on AI and Clinical Decision Making, highlighted the transformative impact of AI technologies in the medical field, particularly their potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy, personalise treatments, and improve patient outcomes. The event featured key presentations from prominent researchers:

- Prof. Giuseppe Boriani and Dr. Davide Antonio Mei (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia) provided an insightful overview of the ARISTOTELES Project, discussing the development of AI-powered models aimed at predicting adverse outcomes and identifying the emergence of new comorbidities in patients with atrial fibrillation.
- Prof. Marco Proietti (Heart Care Foundation) presented an update on the AFFIRMO Project, showcasing how their team is advancing AI-driven apps designed to improve integrated care for patients.
- Prof. Ivan Olier (Liverpool John Moores University) shared progress from the TARGET Project, explaining the role of Digital Twins in AI-based clinical decision-making and its potential in predicting patient outcomes.

The webinar concluded with an engaging Q&A session where participants had the opportunity to interact directly with the speakers, discussing key challenges and ethical considerations surrounding the implementation of AI in healthcare, as well as its impact on clinical practice.

This event highlighted the exciting potential of AI in reshaping the future of healthcare, and the collaboration between these three projects continues to pave the way for advancements in patient care and clinical decision-making.

RAISING AWARENESS AROUND ARISTOTELES

Participation in conferences, fairs, and multiple events

Laboratorio sanità 20/30 Codroipo, Italy

ARISTOTELES project coordinator Professor Giuseppe Boriani took part in the “AI to Transform Healthcare” conference, held on 29–30 May 2025 at the historic Villa Manin in Codroipo (UD), Italy. The event, officially titled the Second Sanità 20/30 AI Laboratory, was organised in collaboration with the Friuli Venezia Giulia Region, Italy, and brought together a diverse audience of healthcare administrators, clinicians, data scientists, and technology partners.

The conference brought together a wide range of voices to explore how AI can be thoughtfully and effectively integrated into healthcare. Over the two days, participants exchanged ideas on how AI can support the care of vulnerable patients, enhance telemedicine, advance bioinformatics,

streamline clinical pathways, and automate healthcare processes—all while addressing the ethical and legal challenges that come with these innovations.

Professor Boriani’s presentation of the ARISTOTELES project was met with great interest and enthusiasm from both researchers and policymakers. His insights into the practical applications of AI in clinical settings and the project's potential to reshape patient care pathways contributed significantly to the event’s success.

The conference underscored the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in shaping the future of healthcare, and Professor Boriani’s contribution exemplified the forward-thinking approach needed to harness AI’s full potential.

ESC Cardio-Oncology 2025 conference

Professor Giuseppe Boriani took part in the ESC Cardio-Oncology 2025 conference held in Florence, Italy, on 20–21 June. The event brought together leading experts from cardiology, oncology, haematology, and related fields to address the growing challenges at the intersection of cancer and cardiovascular care.

During his presentation, Professor Boriani focused on the critical role of data analysis in cardio-oncology, with particular emphasis on atrial fibrillation (AF). He explored the potential implementation of AI in AF management was discussed both in general and in the context of cancer patients, with specific reference to the ongoing ARISTOTELES project.

His contribution reinforced the conference's overarching goal: to foster a more integrated, data-driven approach to cardio-oncology care.

ARISTOTELES stakeholder community

If you're interested in keeping up-to-date with all the latest developments in ARISTOTELES and AI solutions for personalised medicine, we invite you to join our **ARISTOTELES stakeholder community**.

CONSORTIUM MEETING IN AALBORG

On April 10 and 11, 2025, the ARISTOTELES consortium gathered in Aalborg, Denmark, for a two-day meeting that marked an important moment in the project's journey. Hosted by Aalborg University, the event brought together partners from across Europe to share updates, reflect on progress, and plan the next steps in a collaborative and inspiring setting.

Opened by Prof. Martin Bøgsted from the Aalborg University, the meeting proceeded with the first updated on WP1 by the project coordinator Prof. Giuseppe Boriani, who provided an overview of the general state of the project and highlighted key developments since the last consortium gathering.

Throughout the meeting, partners presented the current status of the project, with a particular focus on the core work packages at the heart of ARISTOTELES. Discussions around data integration and modelling (WP4 and WP5) were especially central, as these areas are key to the project's ambition to transform AF and multimorbidity care through advanced digital tools.

In the afternoon of the first day, consortium members were warmly welcomed by Ole Kæseler Andersen, Vice Dean for Research, who introduced the Faculty of Medicine and its impressive research initiatives. The first day included a guided tour of the Faculty of Medicine building, followed by a visit to the new hospital currently under construction next to the faculty. This future facility, with its direct connection to the university, promises to strengthen collaboration between clinical and academic teams.

The meeting was a significant milestone, allowing consortium members to reflect on the progress made thus far and to plan the next steps. The collaborative spirit and shared vision of the ARISTOTELES project were evident as members united to discuss the work ahead, ensuring the project's success over the coming years.

ARISTOTELES the interviews

Meet the People Behind ARISTOTELES: A New Interview Series

We're excited to launch a **new video series** that brings you closer to the researchers behind the ARISTOTELES project. In these short interviews, our team members share what drives their passion for research, what they value most in their work, and how they see their role in shaping the future of healthcare.

This series is designed to introduce the human side of science—highlighting the motivations, insights, and personal stories of the people working to make cardiovascular care more precise, predictive, and patient-centred.

We're kicking things off with a teaser and the first interview featuring the project coordinator, Prof. Giuseppe Boriani, and co-principal investigator, Prof. Gregory Lip. Stay tuned as we continue to release more voices from across the consortium.

**Let's get to know the people behind the project —
click [here](#) to watch the interviews on our YouTube
channel!**

Meet ARISTOTELES' young researchers!

Yun Bing

Dr. Yun Bing, Postdoctoral Research Associate in digital Twins and in silico Clinical Trials at the University of Liverpool and the Liverpool Centre for Cardiovascular Sciences.

As a Postdoctoral Research Associate of WP6, my work involves constructing in silico clinical trials, which includes generating virtual populations, stratifying treatments, and predicting outcomes, to evaluate new AI-powered risk assessment tools for the better management of atrial fibrillation.

Coming from a computational mechanics background, I shifted my focus and pursued a doctoral degree in Biomedical Engineering due to my interests in biology. My expertise lies in mechanistic modelling and numerical analysis. Being part of the ARISTOTELES project not only allows me to apply my existing expertise but also to acquire new knowledge and skills on data analysis and deep learning.

Outside academia, I co-founded a company, Beautiful Voice, where we are developing a digital platform that uses AI and gamification to transform speech and language therapy delivery. In recognition of our work, I was invited by the UK's Prime Minister to No. 10 Downing Street for the celebration of the UK AI ecosystem.

Dr. Adam T. Knowles, Postdoctoral Research Associate at the Data Science Research Centre, Liverpool John Moores University, joins ARISTOTELES to support WP5 in performing data imputation and developing risk prediction modelling using AI and ML methodologies.

Adam T. Knowles

Hi all,

I'm Adam Knowles, a Postdoctoral Research Associate at the Data Science Research Centre within Liverpool John Moores University and an affiliate member of the Liverpool Centre for Cardiovascular Science. I joined ARISTOTELES in January 2025, where my work mainly focusses on WP5 and related deliverables. My primary role centres on applying and advancing ML and AI techniques to firstly impute missing data for the project and then support the development of causal risk prediction models for various outcomes and worsening of comorbidities.

I am excited to be part of this large-scale medical research project, which brings together a diverse collaboration between academia and industry, offering me an opportunity to work in an interesting, impactful and rapidly advancing field. Although my background is in astrophysics, where I completed my Ph.D. modelling stellar populations and galactic chemical evolution, I have always had an interest in research that has measurable benefits in the real-world.

After astronomy-focussed postdoctoral roles in Barcelona and Tenerife, I returned to the UK as an Impact Officer at LJMU, helping researchers across different disciplines plan for, manage and evidence the impact of their research outside of academia. This role further fuelled my passion for research that drives real change in people's lives, making ARISTOTELES's aims to advance personalised healthcare using the latest developments of AI and ML a natural next career step for me.

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Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to follow us on social media to keep upon all the latest ARISTOTELES news!

CONTACT US

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Partners

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